

LYDUS, VINDICIANUS, AND THE CIRCULATION OF LATIN
GYNAECOLOGICAL TEXTS IN SIXTH-CENTURY CONSTANTINOPLE

JOHN LYDUS, HELVIUS VINDICIANUS, AND THE CIRCULATION OF LATIN GYNAECOLOGICAL TEXTS IN SIXTH- CENTURY CONSTANTINOPLE

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the sixth-century historian John Lydus, who, next to an interest in Latin, exhibited a great interest in and knowledge of gynaecological texts. Almost all of his sources on gynaecology are Greek. However, in *Mens.* IV.26, Lydus vaguely mentions his use of Latin sources. We shall compare this passage to the works of the fourth-century Latin physician Helvius Vindicianus, hypothesising that he was one of Lydus' sources. A readership of Vindicianus in Constantinople in the sixth century sheds light on the exchange of medical texts between the "Latin" West and the "Greek" East in late antiquity.

Keywords: *John Lydus, Helvius Vindicianus, late antique gynaecology and embryology, Latin in Constantinople.*

John Lydus: a Learned Bureaucrat with an Interest in Latin

John Lydus, (ca. AD 490 – ca. 565),² was a learned bureaucrat in the praetorian prefecture of the East in Constantinople, where he rose to the prestigious office of *cornicularius*. He made himself noticed to emperor Justinian for whom he delivered, after 530, or after 542, an encomium. John's praise of the emperor impressed Justinian,

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² Ioannes Lydus 75 *PLRE* II.612-615. For introductions to the life and works of John Lydus see Momigliano 1966, p. 187; Carney 1971, pp. 3-19; Bandy 1983, pp. ix-xxxviii; Maas 1992, pp. 28-37; Kelly 2004, p. 11-17; Schamp 2006, pp. xiii-lxxvi; Treadgold 2007, pp. 258-264; Turfa 2012, pp. 8-11; Bandy 2013, pp. 1-29; Bjornlie 2013, pp. 113-117.

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who commissioned a history of his Persian wars (527–532),³ and who promoted John to a teaching position: around 543, Lydus was appointed to a chair of Latin language and literature at the “university” of Constantinople.⁴

In his early teaching years, John composed two of his erudite works,⁵ “On the Months (*De mensibus*)”,⁶ a treatise in four books on Roman chronology, and “On Celestial Signs (*De ostentis*)”,⁷ which formed a compilation of translations from Latin treatises on various portents, and which constituted an elaborate defence of the validity of omens for the prediction of the future.⁸ Around 551-552, John retired from the praetorian prefecture.⁹ However, he probably continued his teaching after he retired from office. In this period, he composed his last treatise, “On the Magistracies of the

³ *Magistr.* III.26. On his *History*, see CHAP 248. Van Nuffelen and Van Hoof 2020, p. xxxi, p. 255.

⁴ In Constantinople, there existed an “institution of higher education”, the precise nature of which remains unclear. Kazhdan 1991, p. 2143. We therefore use the term university as a conventional term. *Magistr.* III.26.1-III.30.10. See Chastagnol 1960, p. 65, n. 58; Caimi 1984, pp. 79-81; Maas 1992, pp. 35-36; Kelly 2004, p. 13; Schamp 2006, pp. xliii-xlv; Domenici 2007, p. 9; Bjornlie 2013, p. 114. Treadgold 2007, p. 261 proposed the earlier date of around 533 for Lydus’ professorship.

⁵ Carney 1971, p. 11; Caimi 1984, pp. 66-68, p. 286; Maas 1992, p. 10; Kaldellis 2003, p. 313; Schamp 2006, pp. xvi-xvii; Domenici 2007, p. 9; Treadgold 2007, p. 261. Internal evidence points to the *De mensibus* being composed before the *De ostentis*, Carney 1971, p. 65; Caimi 1984, pp. 66-68; Schamp 2006, pp. lxxx-lxxxiii, although Lydus might have worked on them simultaneously, Caimi 1984, pp. 66-68.

⁶ CHAP 251. Van Nuffelen and Van Hoof 2020, pp. 256-257. On *De mensibus* see Caimi 1984, pp. 68-71; Schamp 2006, pp. lxxxiv-xcix.

⁷ CHAP 250. Van Nuffelen and Van Hoof 2020, p. 256. On *De ostentis* see Caimi 1984, pp. 71-79; Maas 1992, p. 107, Schamp 2006, pp. xcix-cxv.

⁸ The oeuvre of John Lydus has endured the most problematic textual transmission. Especially the textual transmission of Lydus’ *De mensibus*, Schamp 2006, pp. lxxxiv-xcix, Zingg 2019, p. 558, and, to a lesser extent, *De ostentis*, Schamp 2006, pp. xcix-cxv, is notoriously difficult. In anticipation of the new edition of the *De mensibus*, which is being prepared by E. Zingg, we revert to the edition of Wünsch, published in 1898, which remains, if flawed, the best option currently available, Schamp 2006, p. xciii. E. Zingg was very kind in providing me with remarks on the textual transmission of *De mensibus* and the passage which I discuss in this paper. I am very indebted to his contribution. For the Greek text of *De ostentis*, the use of the second edition of Wachsmuth 1897 is advisable. See Schamp 2006, p. ci.

⁹ On Lydus’ retirement see Carney 1971, p. 11; Caimi 1984, p. 81-83; Schamp 2006, pp. xlv-xlix. The treatise was written after his retirement, Caimi 1984, pp. 81-83, and internal evidence points to the *De magistratibus* having been written after the *De ostentis*, Schamp 2006, p. lxxxiii. Carney 1971, p. 1, 11, dated the *De magistratibus* to the 550’s, with Books I and II written before, and Book III after Lydus’ retirement. Schamp 2006, p. xxxi, placed the composition of the *De magistratibus* after 545. In an elaborate analysis, which also treated the hypothesis of Lydus writing under Justin II, Caimi concluded that the *De magistratibus* was concluded not long after 552, probably in December 554, Caimi 1984, pp. 111-124.

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Roman State (*De magistratibus*)”, in which he described different Roman military and civil institutions from their mythological origins up to the present.¹⁰ He died between 557 and 561.¹¹

As a professor of Latin, John Lydus exhibited an intricate knowledge of and interest in the different aspects of the Latin language.¹² Throughout his works, he quoted several Latin authors, such as Apuleius, Ovid and Vergil.¹³ He upheld his historical argument by various etymological explanations from Latin, and made numerous translations of Latin sources into Greek, most notably in his *De ostentis*.¹⁴

John Lydus and Gynaecology in Late Antiquity

John Lydus exhibited a keen interest in gynaecology and embryology, an interest which, until recently, has remained unnoticed.¹⁵ In the numerous passages which he devoted to this science, John does not abstain from indicating his sources. We give an overview of Lydus’ passages with gynaecological content, alongside a short description, and his sources, in an appendix to this paper.

Despite his interest in the Latin language, the vast majority of John’s sources on gynaecology are Greek sources. Only two passages have a reference to Latin sources. *Ost.* 44¹⁶ has a reference to Apuleius. Apart from this reference, one extensive passage, *Mens.* IV.26,¹⁷ has a vague mention of Lydus’ Latin sources on gynaecology:

¹⁰ CHAP 252. Van Nuffelen and Van Hoof 2020, pp. 257-258. On *De magistratibus* see Schamp 2006, pp cxix-cxxxiii.

¹¹ Maas 1992, p. 11; Schamp 2006, p. xlvi.

¹² For John Lydus’ knowledge of the language as a professor of Latin, see Carney 1971b, pp. 3, 48-49, 48, 61, 129; Caimi 1984, p. 80; Debuissou 1991, p. 56; Rochette 1997, pp. 253-254; Rochette 1998, p. 471, n. 3; Rochette 2012, p. 330; Kaldellis 2005b, p. 8; Schamp 2006, pp. lxxiii-lxxvi; Bowersock 2009, p. 43; Rochette 2012, p. 330. Schamp 2008, p. 37 goes even as far as to characterise Lydus’ knowledge of Latin as “Latinomanie”, as he is one of the Greek authors with the most conspicuous use of Latin. However, Carney 1971b, p. 48 characterised Lydus’ Latin as “shaky.” The readers of John’s works were deemed to know Latin, Baldwin 1995.

¹³ On Apuleius in Lydus, see Baldwin 1982, p. 83. On Lydus’ use of Ovid, see Rota 2017. On the appearance of Vergil in John Lydus see Baldwin 1982, pp. 83-85.

¹⁴ On Lydus’ translations of Latin treatises, see Domenici 2007, p. 8, 28; Turfa 2012, p. 11.

¹⁵ A first overview of John Lydus’ outlook on gynaecology with an analysis of the reasons behind his interest in gynaecology can be found in Praet 2021.

¹⁶ Wachsmuth 1897, pp. 97-98.

¹⁷ Wünsch 1898, pp. 84-86.

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Οἱ τῶν Ῥωμαίων τὴν φυσικὴν ἱστορίαν συγγράφοντες, or, “Those of the Romans who write treatises on natural history.”

In order to trace the possible Latin sources of John Lydus’ gynaecological passage in *Mens.* IV.26, a short digression into the Latin authors on gynaecology in late antiquity is warranted.¹⁸ The gynaecologist Soranus of Ephesus (1st-2nd century)¹⁹ wrote his *Gynaecology* in Greek but enjoyed reasoned popularity in late antiquity in the Latin West through several translations²⁰ and derivative texts.²¹ In the fifth century, he was translated into Latin by Caelius Aurelianus²² and by a person called Muscio or Mustio.²³ The work of Soranus formed the main inspiration for the third book, on gynaecology, of the *Euporiston* of Theodorus Priscianus (late 4th-early 5th century).²⁴ This doctor initially wrote his treatise in Greek but translated it himself into Latin. He migrated from Africa to Constantinople, where he obtained the position of *archiater* at the imperial court. Apart from these works, we can also mention the translation into Latin of two works from the Hippocratic Corpus, *Diseases of Women I and II*, in Italy, between the fourth and sixth centuries,²⁵ and a mass of anonymous compilations, some of them attributed to Galen, Hippocrates, Pliny and even Cleopatra.²⁶

Regrettably, none of the works as we have them now of the above-mentioned authors exhibits any parallel to *Mens.* IV.26 in John Lydus. However, one of the possible sources for this passage in John Lydus is the teacher of Theodorus Priscianus, Helvius Vindicianus. Vindicianus²⁷ was active as a doctor in late fourth-century

¹⁸ For an introduction in the field, see Green 2000, pp. 1-36.

¹⁹ For an introduction into the life and works of Soranus, see Temkin 1956, pp. xxiii-xxv.

²⁰ Temkin 1956, p. xxix, pp. xliv-xlv.

²¹ Green 2000, p. 32. The *Liber geneciae ad Soteris obs[t]etrix* is a late antique conflation of materials from both Pseudo-Cleopatra and Soranus, Green 2000, pp. 18-19. For Pseudo-Cleopatra, see below.

²² Caelius Aurelianus 10 *PLRE* II.201; Green 2000, p. 7.

²³ Mustio *PLRE* II.769; Green 2000, pp. 21-22. Selections from Muscio circulated separately in the treatise *Secreta secretorum mulierum*, Green 2000, p. 28.

²⁴ Theodorus Priscianus 8 *PLRE* I.728; Green 2000, p. 33.

²⁵ Green 2000, p. 11.

²⁶ De Moulin 1964, p. 48. For the anonymous compilations and fragments, see Green 2000, pp. 4, 5, 8, 10, 12, 13, 15, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28, 31, 32 and 34; for Pseudo-Cleopatra, see Green 2000, pp. 8-10; for Pseudo-Galen, see Green 2000, p. 13; Pseudo-Hippocrates, Green 2000, pp. 14-15; Pseudo-Plinius, Green 2000, p. 26.

²⁷ (Helvius) Vindicianus 2 *PLRE* I.967. On this author see Cilliers 2004, pp. 344-346. Also Vindicianus was to some degree indebted to the ideas of his predecessor Soranus, Cilliers 2005, p. 162, 222, 225.

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Carthage. He held several important offices such as the office of the proconsul of Africa and the office of *comes archiatrorum*. Next to the above mentioned Theodorus Priscianus, Vindicianus also counted the church father Augustine amongst his students. One of his works, the *Gynaecia*,²⁸ gives an overview of the different organs and their respective functions. The treatise has an elaborate section on the reproductive system, gynaecology, and embryology, which incorrectly gave its name to the whole of the treatise.²⁹ In the next section, we shall examine the different parallels between these sections on gynaecology and embryology in Vindicianus' *Gynaecia* and section IV.26 in Lydus *De mensibus*.

John Lydus and Helvius Vindicianus

In *Mens.* IV.26, John Lydus gives an overview of the generation of the foetus, the early development of a newborn infant, and the process of disintegration of the human corpse.³⁰ Each of these three phases is structured around the numbers three, nine, and forty.

First, the generation of the foetus is described, with an overview of the first forty days, followed by the further development until birth. In three days, the sperm changes into blood in the uterus and the heart is formed. Lydus mentions that the heart is the first organ to be formed and the last part to disintegrate after death. He continues with an allegorical reading of the number three, explaining that it is an uneven number that is responsible for the process of generation. Next comes the mention of the number

²⁸ The complex transmission history of the *Gynecia* has long precluded an acceptable edition of the text, Cilliers 2005, pp. 154-156. In this paper, we use the reasoned reconstruction of the text as made by L. Cilliers 2005.

²⁹ A short introduction to the *Gynaecia* can be found in Cilliers 2005, pp. 153-154. For an overview of Vindicianus' detailed work on foetal development, see Cilliers 2004, pp. 355-360.

³⁰ The passage enjoyed itself a reasoned popularity in the Middle Ages as a separate treatise, which was erroneously ascribed to different authors such as Splinius (a corruption of Plinius), Libanius and John of Damascus. On this so-called *Tractatum Splinii*, see Wünsch 1898, pp. xxv-xxix; Cumont 1918, p. 278, Ceulemans et al. 2013, p. 62, Zingg 2019, p. 536. The most complete version of the passage is the one in the so-called *Florilegium Coislinianum* Ψ 28, alphabetical anthology dating from the end of 9th to the beginning of the 10th centuries, a recension not known to Wünsch, which has recently been edited by Ceulemans et al. 2013, pp. 75-77. Any reasoning regarding *Mens.* IV.26 should be based on Wünsch's text and the quotation in the *Florilegium Coislinianum*, Zingg 2019, p. 540.

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nine; in nine days the flesh and marrow of the embryo are developed. Finally, in 40 days, all features of the human body are extant.³¹

After the development in the first 40 days of pregnancy, Lydus continues with the development of the foetus until birth, whilst explicitly making the analogy between the first 40 days and the 9 months of the pregnancy: *Ὀμοίως κατὰ ἀναλογίαν τῶν ἡμερῶν καὶ ἐπὶ μηνῶν* or “Likewise analogously with the days it is thus also in the case of the months.”³² In the third month, we have movements of the foetus in the uterus, and by the ninth month the process of human development is completed and the child is born. Next, Lydus dwells on the different developments of girls and boys. Girls are born in nine months, whereas boys are born in ten months. Lydus explains this difference by giving a numerological analysis of the number nine, which is connected to the goddess Selene and to matter, and of the number ten, which is a perfect number. Warm sperm results in quick coagulation which in turn is responsible for a boy, whereas colder semen results in slow coagulation and, in turn, in the development of a girl. Lydus asserts this principle by the observation that aborted male foetuses are fully formed, whereas female aborted foetuses remain unformed.

Second, the development of the foetus is followed by a description of the first 40 days of the newborn infant. Three days after birth the infant loses its swaddling clothes. After nine days it gains strength and endures touch. Finally, after 40 days, an infant can smile and recognize its mother.

The third and last part of *Mens.* IV.26 applies the same numbers 3, 9 and 40 to the process of human disintegration. Three days after death a corpse loses its external features. Nine days *post mortem* all parts of the body dissolve except for the heart. And after 40 days also the heart is the last part of the body to disintegrate. These three stages of human disintegration are taken into account in the commemoration of the dead on the third, ninth and fortieth day after death.³³

³¹ Also Censorinus, *De die natali* 11 states that an embryo is formed in 40 days; Roscher 1907, p. 106.

³² This phrase is, however, not a genuine part of the text of Lydus’ *De mensibus*, Zingg 2019, p. 540, n. 103.

³³ Commemorating the dead on these days is an ancient Christian practice which is already mentioned in the *Apostolic Constitutions*. For a history of this Christian practice in antiquity and late antiquity, and its affinities with pagan practices, see Cumont 1918.

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The parallels between Lydus' statements and the work of Vindicianus can be found in the first part of *Mens.* IV.26, Lydus' description of the process of human development.³⁴ As in the case of John Lydus, Vindicianus *Gyn.* 23, states that the heart is the first organ to be formed and that the whole of human development is completed in 40 days.³⁵

Mens. IV.26 bears furthermore a closer resemblance to chapter 21 of Vindicianus' *Gynecia*.³⁶ This chapter starts with the statement that the human being is completely developed in forty days or in thirty days. Foetuses which develop in 30 days are born in the seventh month, and foetuses that develop in 40 days are born in the ninth month. The chapter continues with a systematic description of the developments in each of the nine months of pregnancy, with the mention of movement in the third month and the birth of the infant in the ninth month. The chapter concludes with remarks on the health of the pregnant woman and on difficulties during labour.

We can see that Lydus borrowed several parts of chapter 21 to upholster his numerological account of human development in *Mens.* IV.26. Lydus namely also mentions the complete development of the foetus in 40 days, and afterwards selected Vindicianus' statements on the third and ninth month to fit his numerological scheme.

Furthermore, the structure of chapter 21 in Vindicianus resembles the structure of Lydus' description. In Vindicianus, a description of the first 30/40 days is followed by an overview of the months. Likewise, Lydus analyses the first 40 days before passing over to a selective overview of the months, "Likewise analogously with the days it is thus also in the case of the months."

Moreover, Vindicianus singles out either the seventh or the ninth month of the pregnancy as the possible moments of birth.³⁷ Vindicianus' avoidance of the eight-

³⁴ Roscher 1907, pp. 104-108, made an analysis of the possible Greek sources and influences, mentioning, next to pythagorean influences, influences of Empedocles, Diocles, Xenocrates, Aristotle and the Stoics. Also Nardi 1971, p. 622, mentions as possible sources as Aristotle, Diocles of Carystus and Empedocles, apparently ignoring that Lydus mentioned Latin sources. Franz Cumont 1918, pp. 278-279, did not believe that Lydus used Latin sources and pointed to a Pythagorean eclectic philosopher such as Numenius.

³⁵ Cilliers 2005, pp. 182-185, p. 227.

³⁶ Cilliers 2005, pp. 180-183.

³⁷ Cilliers 2005, pp. 180-183.

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month³⁸ might have influenced John Lydus, who mentions elsewhere in his *De mensibus* that the eight-month is an ominous month for birth (*Mens.* IV.162):

*The number eight is female, indefinite and imperfect. Hence also Nicomachus calls the eighth month a month of ill-timed birth, as the period of eight months does not stand in any relation to the harmonic principles. Therefore, eight-month foetuses are not born fully developed. Standing between the numbers which bear developed infants, the number eight itself is imperfect. Sharing in every material force, the number takes on powers associated with matter.*³⁹

Returning to *Mens.* IV.26, we can also discern a parallel between Lydus' assertion that warm semen generates male babies and Vindicianus, *Gyn.* 25, which states that a woman pregnant of a boy has a reddish complexion because a boy is warmer than a girl.⁴⁰

In the table below, we give a schematic overview of the parallels described above.

Passage in John Lydus	Parallel Vindicianus
<i>Mens.</i> IV.26 <i>Οἱ τῶν Ῥωμαίων τὴν φυσικὴν ἱστορίαν συγγράφοντες φασιν</i>	
1.1. DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOETUS - 40 FIRST DAYS	
-day 3 sperm changes into blood in the uterus.	

³⁸ Cilliers 2004, p. 362; Cilliers 2005, p. 224.

³⁹ Ὅτι ὁ τῆς ὀγδοῦδος ἀριθμὸς θῆλυς καὶ ἀπειρος καὶ ἀτελής· ὅθεν καὶ παρὰ τῶ Νικομάχῳ ἡλιτόμημος καλεῖται· ὁ γὰρ ὀκτάμημος χρόνος πρὸς οὐδένα τῶν ἀρμονικῶν ἔχων φαίνεται λόγον. Ὅθεν οὐ τελεσφορεῖται τὰ ὀκταμηναῖα· μέσος γὰρ ὢν τῶν τελεσφόρων ἀριθμῶν αὐτὸς ἀτελής εὐρίσκεται. πάσης γὰρ ὑλικῆς δυνάμεως μετέχων τὰς περὶ τὴν ὕλην εἴληφε δυνάμεις. *Mens.* IV.162, Wunsch 1898, p. 177. The viability of the foetus in the seventh month and the unfavorable quality of the eight month were widely accepted in the Greco-Roman world, in Hippocratic writings, Aristotle, Soranus and in Jewish literature; Hanson 1987; Cilliers 2004, pp. 362-363; Cilliers 2005, pp. 223-224.

⁴⁰ Cilliers 2005, pp. 184-187.

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-heart is the first to be formed and the last part which disintegrates.	<i>Vind.23 Primum autem cor hominis fingi dicitur</i>
—3 exegesis: three is a first number and an uneven number which starts the process of generation.	
-day 9 formation of flesh and marrow.	
-day 40 human fully formed.	<i>Vind.21 Omnis enim figura formatur in XL diebus</i> <i>Vind.23</i>
1.2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOETUS - MONTHLY DEVELOPMENT	
<i>Ὁμοίως κατὰ ἀναλογίαν τῶν ἡμερῶν καὶ ἐπὶ μηνῶν</i>	
-month 3 movement in the uterus.	<i>Vind.21 et motum facit infans</i>
-month 9 completion of the foetus. The foetus hastens to exit the womb. <i>ἐπὶ δὲ τοῦ ἐννάτου μηνὸς παντελῶς ἀπαρτίζεσθαι καὶ πρὸς ἔξοδον σπεύδειν.</i>	<i>Vind.21 VIII mense maturum movet infantem natura</i>
-girls born in 9 months, boys in 10 months.	
—9 exegesis Selene, matter 10 exegesis perfection.	
-warm sperm - quick coagulation - boy. -colder sperm - slow coagulation - girl.	<i>Vind.25 et bene rubet in puero quia calidior est puella</i>
—assertion: formed male aborted fetus, unformed female aborted fetus.	

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2. DEVELOPMENT AFTER BIRTH	
-day 3 after birth: child loses swaddling clothes.	
-day 9 after birth: child gains strength and endures touch.	
-day 40 after birth: ability to smile and recognize the mother.	
3. DISINTEGRATION AFTER DEATH	
-day 3 <i>post mortem</i> : loss of external features.	
-day 9 <i>post mortem</i> : dissolution of the body except for the heart.	
-day 40 <i>post mortem</i> : the heart is the last part of the body to dissolve.	
—commemorations of the dead on days 3, 9 and 40 after death.	
<i>Mens. IV.162</i> the eight-month is an ill-timed moment for birth.	<i>Vind.21 qui vero in XXX diebus formatur in VII mense nascitur, qui autem in XL diebus formatur in VIII mense nascitur.</i>

The Circulation of Latin Medical Texts in Sixth-century Constantinople

John Lydus' borrowings from the Latin *Gynecia* of Helvius Vindicianus shed further light on the circulation of Latin medical texts in the Greek eastern part of the later Roman Empire. At some point in time, Vindicianus' *Gynecia* migrated from Africa to

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Constantinople, most possibly with the help of Vindicianus' pupil Theodorus Priscianus, who is known to have moved from Africa to Constantinople.

Our analysis shows that the Latin treatise of Vindicianus had a readership in Constantinople as late as the sixth century, in a period in which there was an intense and continuous exchange of both medical texts as medical personnel between the Latin western and the Greek eastern parts of the (former) Roman Empire.

In the Ostrogothic realm of Theoderic (493–526), there was an intense interest in and proliferation of technical and medical texts,⁴¹ which might have been transferred to Constantinople, after the byzantine conquest of Ostrogothic Italy (535–540) and the exodus of the Ostrogothic court to Constantinople. For instance, the intellectual and Ostrogothic bureaucrat Cassiodorus (ca. 485 – ca. 585)⁴² conceived during his service in the Ostrogothic state of a translation program of logical and mathematical works, and had a keen interest in medicine and architecture.⁴³ After the toppling of the Ostrogothic regime,⁴⁴ Cassiodorus went to Constantinople,⁴⁵ perhaps with some of the medical texts which he had translated and copied.⁴⁶ After his stay (or detention) in Constantinople (ca. 540 – 554),⁴⁷ he founded his Vivarium monastery in the South of Italy, which benefitted from Cassiodorus' close connection with the scriptoria of Ravenna for its scientific and practical texts.⁴⁸ Significantly, in his theoretical outline of Christian higher learning, the *Institutions on Divine and Secular Learning*,⁴⁹ Cassiodorus mentions Caelius Aurelianus, one of the Latin sources on gynaecology.⁵⁰

⁴¹ Baader 1985; Cracco Ruggini 2008.

⁴² An overview of the life, career, and works of Cassiodorus can be found in Schanz 1920, pp. 92-95; Carney 1971b, pp. 97-99; O'Donnell 1979; Giardina 2006, pp. 22-25; Bjornlie 2013, pp. 16-19; Bjornlie 2017, pp. 434-438; Lozovsky 2016, pp. 322-324.

⁴³ Cracco Ruggini 2008, pp. 30-31, gives an elucidating sketch of Cassiodorus' scientific activities during his political career.

⁴⁴ Vessey 2004, pp. 14-15; Heydemann 2016, pp. 36-40.

⁴⁵ Van de Vyver 1931, pp. 254-260; Momigliano 1966, p. 193; O'Donnell 1979, pp. 105-107; Vessey 2004, pp. 14-15; Bjornlie 2013, pp. 17-18. On the evidence of Cassiodorus' stay in Constantinople, see Momigliano 1966, pp. 191-193; O'Donnell 1979, pp. 132-133.

⁴⁶ On the medicinal science in Cassiodorus' *Variae*, see Marano 2011, *Var.* II.39 and Lozovsky 2016, pp. 319-320; *Var.* VI.19.

⁴⁷ Momigliano 1966, p. 193; O'Donnell 1979, pp. 131, 135.

⁴⁸ Cracco Ruggini 2008, p. 29. On the transmission of medicinal texts at Vivarium specifically, see Courcelle 1943, pp. 382-388.

⁴⁹ Schanz 1920, pp. 103-105; Peretto 1993, p. 219.

⁵⁰ *Inst.* I.XXI.2; Mynors 1937, p. 79; *PLRE* II.201; Courcelle 1943, p. 384.

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The exchange of medical texts in the sixth century was also accompanied by an exchange of medical personnel. A noteworthy example in this regard is the career of the Greek physician Anthimus (ca. 475 – ca. 525) at the courts of the Ostrogothic king Theodoric and the Frankish king Theuderic I.⁵¹ Closer to the network of John Lydus, the Lydian physician Alexander of Tralles (ca. 525 – ca. 605) settled in Rome after having travelled and practised in Spain, Italy and Gaul.⁵² This Alexander was the brother of Anthemius of Tralles, one of the architects of the Hagia Sophia church, who can be connected to the network of the praetorian prefect Phocas – a network to which John Lydus also belonged.⁵³

As regards John Lydus, we could situate his consultation and use of the *Gynecia* within the common practice in antiquity of an interested lay public which read medical texts. John Lydus read Greek and Latin texts on gynaecology and embryology to mine these texts for data that he could use in his own narrative.⁵⁴

However, one question remains as to Lydus' use of Vindicianus. If John Lydus took a great interest in showcasing his knowledge of Latin sources, predominantly by citing or naming them, why did he not mention Vindicianus by name? As mentioned above, Lydus in *Mens.* IV.26 only vaguely referred to “Those of the Romans who write treatises on natural history.” A possible answer could be found in the perceived lowly status of Vindicianus' work, which Cilliers describes as:

*It was most probably written as a textbook for young medical students, or as a vademecum for doctors when travelling, or as a self-help book in private houses, in short, a kind of “Idiot’s Guide” on medical matters.*⁵⁵

⁵¹ Anthimus 3 *PLRE* II.100.

⁵² Alexander 8 (of Tralles) *PLRE* III.44-45; Kaldellis 2013, p. 356.

⁵³ On the network of Phocas, Alexander of Tralles and John Lydus, see Kaldellis 2013. Another link which could connect Alexander of Tralles to John Lydus is their common origin in Lydia. On the importance of local ties for furthering one's career in the administration, see Kelly 2004, pp. 173-174, 184-185. For the presence and danger of cliques in the bureaucracy which were based on local ties see Kelly 2004, pp. 48-49.

⁵⁴ Praet 2021.

⁵⁵ Cilliers 2005, p. 153.

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Perhaps Lydus was not that keen to show to his readers that his knowledge of the development of the foetus derived from a basic introduction to the subject. Moreover, we could mention Lydus' antiquarian tendency to mention only sources from hallowed antiquity, passing over in silence more recent works.⁵⁶

Appendix

Passage	Description	Sources Mentioned
<i>Mens.</i> II.12	The perfection of infants born in seven months.	Hippocrates, <i>Περὶ Ἑπταμήνων</i> , Kühn, <i>Medicorum Graecorum Opera</i> , I.444 = <i>Doxographi Graeci</i> 428a16b Plato, <i>Timaeus</i> 36D
<i>Mens.</i> IV.26	The development of the foetus, the development after birth, and the disintegration after death.	“Those of the Romans who write treatises on natural history”
<i>Mens.</i> IV.31	An infant does not require food in the womb.	
<i>Mens.</i> IV.40	An infant does not have teeth in the womb.	Stoics <i>Doxographi Graeci</i> 486a8 sqq.
<i>Mens.</i> IV.65	Myrtle strengthens the body of the newly born child.	
<i>Mens.</i> IV.66	Women with the opening of their uterus in a straight line are prolific, but	“The natural philosophers”

⁵⁶ On John's avoidance to cite later and inferior sources and on his predilection of namedropping prestigious, ancient sources, see Carney 1971b, pp. 30, 52, 53, 64, 91, 57-58.

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	that those having it in a crooked line are barren.	
<i>Mens.</i> IV.80	An infant walks before it talks.	Numenius
<i>Mens.</i> IV.84	The opinions of Plato and Empedocles on the causes of monstrous births.	Plato (Strato) <i>Doxographi Graeci</i> 421a1, Empedocles <i>Doxographi Graeci</i> 420a20
<i>Mens.</i> IV.89	Drinking of cold water during the festival of Hera against the occurrence of twin births or monstrous births. Miraculous multiple births during the reign of Hadrian.	Aristotle, <i>Historia Animalium</i> VII.4 Heraclides
<i>Mens.</i> IV.102	The month <i>Quintilis</i> changed into <i>Julius</i> because Caesar was born in July.	“The ancients”, “The historians”, Valens <i>Hist. Rom. Fragm.</i> (ed. H. Peter 378)
<i>Mens.</i> IV.105	Caesar born in seven months. His birth is the reason for the change of the month’s name and the reason for his prodigy.	“Many of the historians”
<i>Mens.</i> IV.106	Advice to women to abstain from sexual activity in July, to preserve their health.	
<i>Mens.</i> IV.148	Information on the protective goddesses in childbirth: Ilithyia and Artemis.	Plutarch
<i>Mens.</i> IV.162	The eight-month of the pregnancy is an ominous month for birth.	Ps.-Nicomachus, <i>Theologumena Arithm.</i> p. 55,25 Ast.

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Ost. 44	Abortion of the pregnant Marcia, spouse of Cato, by the thunderbolt Arges/Lampros.	Apuleius
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Abbreviations

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